

- 4) OrdZm HSZHSKQS
- 5) AnaUmUrdVrd^rdZm
- 6) gmr(OHd ArfVXOndng
- 7) Arfa`ŠVrgKf©
- 8) OrdZmI anAWPa(dUdE`nr_Zigm(OHSHUjsanaM.

- AZde
- MfHS rZHSKQS
- Odagm(ZHSKQSBÈ nr O{dHSKQSBAdgn {dHW`À nHau KQHSÜ oAŸ^@ huzmXgz `Vm
- * gÈmZ(df`ndab gÈmZmArli`HS/m

EHSgdnoeVHSnoM{VHSrnyMeVHAgz EHS-nog _zdr OrdZmXO@CYMÊ igrdè _mèna`rdr à`ÈZ gÈSAgz Xgè m-nog dnr ~Hr, _hnr© dnrVoI rJrHU, Z{VHS`w`ndng, ArfVXOndng BÈ nr Haur`r \_z{gHS VrImYZ. Ordna`mì`ŠVtMà`r dnr ArhArfU`mKQHSmì`ŠVr OrdZ gVrUoÜ oASW nRav ArhEHS-nog A{Vcf JW gÈmZ HSUm(dUrMvXgè m-nog nrHÈ mAnò m nVPHVnz Arè`zdzae Prä`zArh`hÈ nHUm(dUrMvEHMdo g Xgz `Vm. ~SbmJr; ngnBÈ nr ^rVHS gVg(dYmAgVzm _z{gHS enVgrdè EI rüm`RnÜ oOrhml r`Ÿ dJ©Xgz `Vm EHSUMAem Adgn {dHW`M`\_Zigm(OHSHUoemÊ igrdè d`à{V`ŸZmZdrZ`_m{gMÊ igrdè`ànVw {df`m gÈmZigrdè {ZdS`HÈ`r Arhr

- 2) gÈmZmC{Qo
- 1) Adgn {dHW`M`_mZ`HsUo
- 2) Adgn {dHW`r`ndab`\_Zigm(OHSHU`KQHS`\_mZ`HsUo
- 3) gÈmZmJrVHS
- 1) Adgn {dHW`À`né`UrÜ`dVrd`ArfVgY`nd`r`A{YHSXgz`È.
- 2) Adgn {dHW`r`CX`dÊ`mno`\_Zigm(OHSHU`h`^rd`A{YHSXgz`È.

- 4) gÈmZ`nÖVr
- A) Z`ZmZds>

ànVw Aä`igrdè`Bromy, Hs>`güran`gür, Hsümy`eharib {d{dY`_Zm`Ur``rÜ`oAdgn {dHW`ndab`CnMangr`^avr`Prhè`né`UrM`{ZdS`HÈ`r Arhr`È`nd`mQ`d`df}17`Vc60`BVHrüm {d{dY`ej`{UH`gmr(OH`ArfVX`^nr`rHS`nvanYZ`Arhè`m30`ór`néf`é`UrM`Z`ZmahUZ`{ZdS`HÈ`r Arhr

B) _mZ`grZzo

ànVw gÈmZmÜ`o`rnr`{`i`{dÊ`igrdè`I`nd`\_zgerór`MUrMdmaHÈ`r Arhm

I) ArfVgY`MUr

Sähe`r`Hr`ArfU`Säann(Vdar (1971)`nr`V`m`Hö`mArfVgY`MUr`Ü`né`Ur`mArfVgY`nd`r`m`_mZ`HÈ`r Arh`ànVw`ArfVgY`MUr`qXr`Ü`oAgz``mMUrV`EHU`96`äiz`ArhV.`àÈ`ÈS

àizigndemmn`m Agz`de n`mg_m"✓ AerIÛ HmM AgVoMMUmeHU ààfShmAnfgY
 nli rgW HUmZXEfSg_Obn0m mJWfSUméUà nAnfgY nli rMAV H_r, H_r, _Ü_,
 VidArfU A{VidAnfgY AemMafSmÜ dJfHU Hb0no

I I) OrdZ dñ nÖVr

ànVWgēnZmÜ oAnfgY MMUr-aaMéUà m-mVv Adgn {dH/rhû igrE È à nOrdZmb Á`m
 _Zigm(OHSHU KQHhgh^nl AhoVouhÊ igrE OrdZdñ nÖVrmdma HÊ ñ Arbm`mÖVrÀ m
 _ñi`nZ éU, éUmmZndfS {\_Ì, ghHr`è Hsz {d{dY OrdZ n{anWw; éUmmrd^nd BÈ ñr
 {df`r`ñVr {i{dÊ ñ Arbr. éUmm(dHwmd`i {SV\_îd, {dHwZYAmi`{SV_îd, gÚHbz gm(OH
 n{anWw; ddr(hSn{anWw; Ar(hSn{anWw; Hgf`HArñad; [SVHgsy, Hgf`H_Z(mHfHBEVhg,
 gÚHbz ArOmMfVhg BÈ ñr KQHm`ñVrKê ñ Arbr.

5) gš`æór` {dib6U d MM

ànVWgēnZmÜ o`ñVrMgš`H` {dib6U HÊ igrE Adgn {dH/rA méUmsZ gñdz Kóbö`m
 AnfgY nli rMMUÀ mJWfHhgagar_Ü HÊ ñ Arbm

Adgn {dH/rda{d{dY éUhb`mÜ CnMaKuà néUà nAnfgY nli mGagarXe@UmVŠVm
 VŠVnH 1

Adgn {dH/rda{d{dY éUhb`mÜ CnMaKuà néUà nAnfgY nli mGagar

Adgn éU	Z_zm	gagar Jwfs(_Ü fS)	ñni HBU
ór	17	197.88	VidAnfgY
néf	13	180.62	VidAnfgY
EHU	30	183.20	VidAnfgY

Adgn {dH/rgrE {d{dY _Zia`Uhb`mÜ CnMaKuà néUà Adgn {dH/rMZoH_mZ HÊ igrE
 ArfU {dH/r`ñib`_Zigm(OHSHU KQHhAä igr HÊ igrE ànVWgēnZ hñr Kê ñ Arbo
 dab VŠÈ mÜ oXe@è`m`ñi{d{dY _Zia`Uhb`mÜ CnMāY Pñbõ`m30 Adgn éU`m Adgn
 nli mGagar Jwfs183.20 BVHArhoArfU`mJWfSMñni`HBU VidAnfgY Agd_i`hoVgMór
 éU`mGagar Jwfs197.88 BVHAgz`mñni`HBU VidAnfgY Ago\_i`hoArfU néf éU`m
 gagar Jwfs180.62 BVHAgz`mñni`HBUr VidAnfgY Ago_i`ho`hUOMgÜ`à mŠññi
 AdgnMa`ñi VidVodñV ArhoArfU néf`mVbZZo`ó`ñYib AdgnMa`ñi A{YHVid«Agè`m
 {Xgz`VoVgM{d{dY \_Zia`Uhb`mÜ AdgnM30 éU`m CnbāY PñhAgz`È mH 17 óréU`d 13 néf
 éU`m Arhv.`mÉZ EHUmq`ñar Hñr AgVn100 Adgn éU`mH 55.67% óréU`d 43.33% néf
 éU`m hñ`mÉZ néf`mVbZZo`ó`ñi Adgn {dH/rMa`ñi A{YHAgè`mXgz`Vo

Arbõ H\$ 1

Adgn{dHrda{d{dY é½Urb`mÜ`cnMaKÜrà nór- néf é½Urb`Q.6har

`zYa Adgn{dHrÀ né½Urb`gndZ Kwbö`mAnrgY` mDi MJUzH\$ zgnadJHBU HboAgVm
 30 nH 9 é½Urb`H\_r AnrgY, 7 é½Urb`_Ü_ AnrgY, 12 é½Urb`Vrd«AnrgY AnU 2 é½Urb`m
 A{Vrd«AnrgY Agè`mXgz` Arbo`ndéZ Vrd«Adgn{dHrÀ mé½Urb`odT`hd Agè`mXgz` `Vo
 àhUOMgè`Zmdu`sbbr{gÕHènZnH\$ H\$1 ñdHr Prä`mXgz` `Vo

Arbõ H\$ 2

Adgn{dHrda{d{dY é½Urb`mÜ`cnMaKÜrà né½Urb`Yib Adgn{dHrMnDi r

VgMAdgn é½Urb`mAdgn`ZndHr`nrb`HBU KCHf`r`ñdVr KwAgoXgz` `VoH\$ H\$H\$H\$
 _V^k qHndmivoAdgn{dHr`hd`m`g\$`ngdr`OmV àhUOo13 BVH\$ Arbo`zYa Zmdu`Ar{VH\$
 qHm^`dî`n`m`Vowo7, ej {UH\$g`ñ`owo4, em{H\$AOramwo3, Odi`À`mì`ŠVrÀ`m`Ë`wy`o2 AnU
 ì`ŠV`Ël`KCH`qHm`ñd`mivo1`ì`ŠVr`Adgn{dHrM`Agbbr`{Xgz` `Vo`àhUOMH\$H\$H\$ Ar{VH\$
 ej {UH\$g`ñ`mivoAdgn{dHr`hd`m`g\$`ngdr`OmV`àhUOo13 BVH\$ Arbo`zYa Zmdu`Ar{VH\$
 ñdHr Prä`mXgz` `Vo

6) Cngln

A) {ZiH[©]

1) AdgM {dHwÀ né }UmÜ dVd«AnrgY` AgÊ mÀ\_ri A{YHAgè mXgz `Vo

2) AdgM {dHwMa_ri néfî nVbZvqó` nÜ a{YHAgè mXgz `Vo

3) AdgM {dHwÀ m_ZigmqOHSBü KQHSÜ aZHS zHr; AnVBSqMm^ {d` mHsinOr, ej {UHS
g_n memaHArOm Odi À m` ŠVrM\_Ë yArU i` {ŠV_Îd KQHSË nR KQHSMAy^ @ Xgz `Vm

B) _`nM

àñWAä` iggrR {ZdSbNZ`_nd g_n m` rKV rlenM\_Ë` nArV.

C) {e\Šer

àñWAä` iggrR {dñV j ònub Z`_ZnArU AdgM {dHwM AZHSAS nR Aä` ig Hâ` igRr i` mHj ò
KQZ i` mHsidénM g`nZ hrR Km ò.

D) Cnm` rZm

1) OrdZHSa{YHgHrî HSÑi HZmZ nHuo

2) OrdZ g_nZmZHF^ rVHSKQHS gSSVZ bndUo

3) i` ŠVig Vrî i` dñVnZÀ nZdz nÖVr {eHdUo

4) g_n ñ Hn|anWr_YZ` eñd|aË m\_ranSUmab`_Ë C^mHuo

5) HqH SAraHS oÜ g_VnUnHuoË nR_ri`\_mZ AdgM {dHwda {Z`_ŠU ArUoeŠ`_hñ. VgM
`\_te`_ZgmManÖVrMrdmaHrnbndm

* gX^gM

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